

between LC and GSC was moderate to good. Narrower limits of agreement were generally evident regarding samples showing lower values. The results of this study indicate that method agreement between analysis chambers can be variable and affect CASA outcomes. This fact should be considered when comparing the results from different laboratories.

P72 | 3-Hormonal complex in early pregnant mares

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The aim of the work was to study the interaction (levels and ratio) of progesterone (P4), 17 β estradiol (E2) and equine chorionic gonadotropin (eCG) hormones in 19 pregnant mares depending on age (<10 and \geq 10 yo), and reproductive status (lactating or non-lactating). Hormones levels were analyzed on days 25, 35, 45 and 55 of gestation by RIA (P4 and E2) and ELISA (eCG, from day 35). Simultaneously, the number, size of follicles (F) and corpus luteum (CL) in ovaries, and conceptus state were examined by US-scanner. Data were statistically analyzed by Student-Fischer *t*-test. Results showed large (>30 mm) F were observed in 42.1% and 73.6% of the mares on day 25 and 35, respectively. No relationship between size of F and E2 level was established. Secondary CL was found in ovaries of two mares on day 35 and in all of them on day 45. The average level of each hormone increased ($P < 0.05$) between days 25, 35, 45 and 55, respectively (P4: 13.0, 19.6, 26.6, 32.7 ng/ml; E2: 77.8, 111.8, 147.2, 196.3 pg/ml; eCG: ND, 3.8, 18.8, 43.5 IU/ml) without significant differences between lactating ($n = 9$) and non-lactating ($n = 8$) mares. The average eCG level was higher in young (<10 years, $n = 13$) than in older mares (\geq 10 years, $n = 5$), on day 45 (20.46 and 11.0 IU/ml, $P < 0.05$) and 55 (52.3 and 18.2 IU/ml, $P < 0.001$). The individual levels of hormones and their combination on days 25, 35, 45 and 55 of gestation showed high variability in mares. However, there was some stability of this hormonal complex within certain limits for each stage of pregnancy. In average, this was similar between lactating and non-lactating mares.

P73 | The role of mycoplasma infections in mastitis and reproductive pathologies in cows

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One of the main reasons for the reduction of reproduction in farms are mycoplasma infections of cattle, leading to disturbances in the reproductive system and mastitis of cows. The aim of the study was

to study the participation of mycoplasma in the development of reproductive disorders and udder infections. Materials and Methods: DNA isolation was carried out using DNA sorb B kits (FBSI Central Research Institute of Epidemiology of Rospotrebnadzor, Russia). In order to identify *Mycoplasma* spp. a study of the material was carried out by PCR with electrophoretic detection. For the amplification process, we used the Tertsik device manufactured by DNA Technology LLC (Russia). In order to molecularly identify *M. bovis* and *U. diversum*, the material was studied using real-time PCR in a microarray version with the simultaneous detection of *Mycoplasma bovis* and *Ureaplasma diversum* (Lumex GC, Russia). For amplification, RT-PCR cyclers AriaDNA with a microchip with lyophilized reagents developed by IC Lumex was used. The results of the study: In the farms of the North-West region, from 242 samples from cows, in $n = 120$ *Mycoplasma* spp. were detected. Of these, 57 samples ($n = 19$, vaginal mucus; $n = 19$, milk and $n = 19$, aborted fetuses) were positive for *Mycoplasma bovis* (47%). In $n = 63$ samples *U. diversum* was isolated ($n = 44$, vaginal mucus and $n = 19$, aborted fetuses ($n = 19$)). The association of *Mycoplasma bovis* and *U. diversum* was identified in $n = 19$ samples from animals with vulvovaginitis and mastitis, as well as of aborted fetuses. It was concluded that *Mycoplasma bovis* was an important cause of contagious mastitis and reproductive infections in cows.

P74 | Neospora caninum associated with cattle epidemic abortion

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The study presents the results of serological monitoring of *N. caninum* in 18 dairy herds of the Sverdlovsk region in Russia and the characteristics of neosporosis on a farm with epidemic abortions of up to 24.7%. Seropositive animals were identified in 10 agricultural organizations. Antibodies to *N. caninum* were registered in 58 (29.9%) of 194 tested samples by ELISA. In farms with identified seropositive animals, the seroprevalence was 43.3%. During 2019, abortions were registered in 63/659 pregnant cows (9.6%). Moreover, the largest number of abortions ($n = 50$) was registered at one of the farms, which corresponded to 24.7% of pregnant cows. The average gestational duration at abortion was 165.8 ± 4.6 days. Among 63 aborted cows, 51 (80.9%) cows had a pregnancy loss within 140–235 days. A case-control study was conducted to study the infectious causes of abortion in one of the farms of the Sverdlovsk region. From the 63 aborted cows, $n = 33$ and $n = 10$ normally pregnant cows were the objects of the research. Seroprevalence for *N. caninum* was established in 40.7% of the studied animals. In the group of aborted cows 100.0% of animals were seropositive, in the group of pregnant cows 11.1%. A histological examination revealed that the development of the aborted fetal organs and the placenta corresponded to the indicated pregnancy periods. Chronic pathological processes were not detected in the placenta, chorionic villi were preserved. There

were dramatically overflowing blood vessels from capillaries to large blood vessels and destruction of a surface epithelium connecting partly fetal and maternal placenta, which is typical for spontaneous abortion. In the heart, lungs, liver of aborted fetuses and in the placenta, significant numbers of neospores were found.

P75 | Growth and development of Bashkir foals in conditions of the forest zone of the Middle Urals

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The patterns of foal growth and development were studied in the peasant farm enterprise «Idiyatullin Kh.S.». Young animals of the same live weight were divided into two groups of $n = 10$ each. The control group included early spring (April-May) foals. The experimental group consisted of late birth (June-July) animals. The dynamics of live weight and linear measurements were analyzed at parturition and at the age of 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. Foals born in April and May had a larger live weight at birth and throughout the whole observation period. These animals had higher total body weight gain at 12 months of age (by 19 kg) than the late foals. The average daily gain of the latter was lower by 300–600 g ($P < 0.05$). Growing measurements of early-spring foals gradually left behind all indicators of late animals and at the age of 12 months, they were ahead by 2 cm in the shoulder, by 1 cm in the body, and by 1 cm in the heart girth. These data indicate that early foals' mothers made good use of pastures rich in all nutrients during the main growth and development of the fetus. Before the beginning of the grazing season early foals are already accustomed to eating all types of feed, which has a positive effect on the development of the gastrointestinal tract. Early foals are grazing 2–3 months earlier than late foals. Earlier use of pastures contributes to better development of the body. Thus, in the conditions of the Middle Urals, we recommend April and May as the best time for foaling of Bashkir mares. It provides the growth and development of stronger and healthier foals being one of the major reserves to enhance horsemeat production.

P76 | Effect of vitamin C and pentoxifylline on semen parameters of thawed stallion semen

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The aim of the study was to evaluate the influence of antioxidants (vitamin C and pentoxifylline) on equine sperm parameters after thawing. Six straws (0.5 ml) of frozen-thawed stallion semen with 10×10^6 spermatozoa/ml were supplemented with 5 mM vit C and 7 mM of pentoxifylline (Pent) immediately after thawing. Two replicates per ejaculate were evaluated for each treatment. The semen

parameters were determined by CASA (Microptic, Spain). Sperm morphology was estimated with sperm blue staining. Sperm vitality was analyzed by BrightVit kit. The activity of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), alkaline phosphatase (AP), γ -glutamyl transferase (GGT) and creatine kinase (CK) in seminal plasma, water and triton X-100 sperm extracts were made by chemistry analyzer BA-88 (Mindray, Germany). The values for the total motility assessed in treatment 7 mM Pent was 93.4 ± 7.9 , in control group was 52.02 ± 2.3 . It was not significantly different from the vitality of spermatozoa in controls (71.11 ± 3.1 with Pent and 66.35 ± 2.8 in control). The addition of vit C did not improve the post thaw motility and viability of spermatozoa compared with the control ($P > 0.05$). However, the addition of 7 mM Pent to cryopreserved semen immediately after thawing significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased total motility and non-significantly affected the vitality of spermatozoa compared to controls. The enzyme activities of AP and LDH in samples that were treated with vit C and Pent were higher ($P < 0.05$) than the control, while GGT and CK had been reduced but not significantly. No statistical differences were observed in enzyme activities between treatments. In conclusion, Pent increased the post thaw motility of cryopreserved stallion semen when added after thawing. This research was supported by NNP Reprobiotech, MES Bulgaria.

P77 | Changes of boar sperm proteins and characteristics due to seasonal infertility period

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Swine seasonal infertility affects the productivity of a pig farm. The elevated environmental temperatures and the photoperiod in the summer season have been mentioned as main causes of infertility. The aim of the study was to investigate which sperm proteins and sperm variables are affected at the period of seasonal infertility. Depending on the environmental temperatures, the period October-June was considered as cold (mean temperature 12.5°C) and the period July-September as warm season (mean temperature 23.9°C). 65 ejaculates from 18 boars were collected over a year. Each semen sample was evaluated for kinetics (Computer Assisted Semen Analyzer), morphology (Sperm Blue stain), viability (Propidium Iodide – Calcein AM stain), mitochondrial membrane potential (Rhodamine 123 – Propidium Iodide stain), membrane biochemical functionality (Hypo-osmotic swelling test) and sperm DNA integrity (Acridine Orange Test). Moreover, seminal plasma and sperm selected proteins (HSP90, GPX5, OPN) were detected and quantified by Western Blot. Depending on the distribution of the data, a Wilcoxon's two sample test or a two-sample t-test for independent observations was used. Straight line velocity (VSL), linearity